

	Participant-1	Participant-2	Participant-3	Participant-4	Participant-5	Total
Researcher Findings						
Number of findings	8	7	4	10	7	36
Useful / Interesting Features						
production places	1			I really always like a map tool that's like, super handy.		1
production heatmap	1					
connected historical events	1		listing of objects according to historical events	many filters, especially historical events		1
acquisition dates	1 (I liked the acquisition by origin timeline, but acquisition date is more handy)		1 (timeline)			
Include and exclude filter		extensive filtering and visualisation	1 (sometimes, we are searching for values and you don't want that values and excluding it is not an option.)	visualisation of date and other list		
Actor-Actor Network	1		1 (The network seems most logical way to get to the actor, if you do not know a specific name to look for -- I like seeing networks)		I am quite enthusiastic about the network views. I think the most logical way to understand people is also through connections. And this is not something the TMS can do. I mean, you can sometimes sort of browse through it, but I find this is a very visual way of seeing.	
Related Tabs				additional tab specially for provenance and connections		
Hyperlinks	1 (historical event's option + all the connections)	1 (connections between actors/objects/events etc.				
Provenance Tab					1	
Actor-acquisition timeseries				Found some inconsistencies in persons acquisition timeline 1922 and also 2011. Super interesting! This is something I wouldn't find out otherwise without this view.		
Multiple Perspectives		various starting point of research				
Limitation of the Data Eco System						
Limitation of the Data						
	You can immediately see that the data has not been recorded and it doesn't appear.	Interesting Wereldmuseum has only 4 objects! --> different identifier used; it is not known to the data that it is sameAs some other museum which is actually mention in its remarks.	selecting congo as place of origing and looking into the statistics summary by provenance type, P3 said, I already knew it. It show the real work has to be done (as provenance type just showed the manner of provenance event is not known)	So I really always like a map tool that's like, super handy. So I'm going to Nias because that's where I did my research. And I can already see. [looking at the production place, identifying different region from nias]: General Nias, the region, the island abd souther Nias. Going in to Acquisition dates, found out only 3 objects (out of 31) has acquisition date..."Aaaah! This is good to know" --> lack of acquisition date	I saw something from Indonesia, so lets look into that. It is interesting to me because I was talking about this (RV-11671-10) gate the other day. This is interesting. Museum Volkenkunde has a photo of a gate.. its for Thakranagara, I don't know much about Indonesia, but we were talking about the gates the other day.. I was looking for a photo on the website and I couldn't find it. So, it has come from Volkenkundig Museum 'Justinus van Nassau' from Breda. But I could not see when it is transferred. I know I typed that in the TMS field but probably not in a computer readable field.	
			In the TMS, it might also be object has an title from the maker/provenance actor themselves (how the actor describes this object). Including that could be interesting, according to P3.	you have to have narrowed down and see in the annual report if there are any objects recorded coming from him, the person. What is the object number? OK, let's see. So but if I go, this is now all an NMVW, right? Yes. OK. If I go... Doesn't say wait where it's located right now. Which museum.... I mean, I can read it from the object number. It's odd! Like in TMS, you have the location, I guess in a specific folder you have, where it is currently stored in which depot. But this... yeah, this would be something interesting to see, which collection it is in. So you know which annual report to look into. --> lack of information on object's current location, makes it difficult to find out which annual report to focus on.		
			Looking into the actor-actor network P3 sees "Rijksmuseum Volkenkunde" which is wereldmuseum today have only limited connection to other actors, which is not a lot! That is suprising --> Multiple identifier and no resolution between them.	actor-acquisition timeseries showed transfer date to museum in the '920's but also in 2011! https://pmsampo.demo.seco.cs.aalto.fi/en/collections/page/83235/provenance what happened there?		
			Interested in to actor named: "prof. dr. A.A. Gerbrands", wanted to know connected actors to this person, find out only one object related to this person. P3 commented: "says a lot of potential, but it is really limited to the data. "			
			Exploring the actor-actor network graph, P3 say: "There is one more actor who could be wereldmuseum, it says "Stichting National Museum van Wereldculturen" "			
			P3 asked: Is the provenance events chronological? Interviewer: No, as we do not have the date for the particular event.			
			It is interesting to see it as network, but the extent to it is really limited by the data to get to actual findings			
Limitation of TMS or others						

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			check for network / related actor did we only take "from actor" or also to actor is there?			
Interesting Findings						
Contradiction of existing Belief						
	Looking into Actor "Natura Artis Magistra" object Acquisition date timelines, surprised to see only two different date of acquisition.	Looking at the 11 objects from Tapanahoni river [laughed], they are all gifted!!!	so, everthing is Dutch (new information, confirming soft belief)	So, I really always like a map tool that's like, super handy. So I'm going to Nias because that's where I did my research. And I can already see, [looking at the production place, identifying different region from nias]: General Nias, the region, the island and souther Nias. Going in to Acquisition dates, found out only 3 objects has acquisition date..."Aaaah! This is good to know"	This is interesting to me that we got an Indonesian objects from Germans which is non-obvious story to me.	
	Actor "Natura Artis Magistra" --> production heatmap, going back to the production place of origin, very surprised to see object from Futila.	Interesting Werelmuseum has only 4 objects!	... two different place with 17 objects and 14 objects (where totally selected 17 objects), the participant was surprised to see that (underlying belief system, one object should have one place of origin); now clicking onto the place of origin from the object instance page, the P3 updates her belief, say "ok. I see!"			
new information (serendipitous)						
				originally interested in Koninklijk Nederlands Aardrijkskundig Genootschap (KNAG), but found out another institute Maatschappij ter Bevordering van het Natuurkundig Onderzoek der Nederlandsche Kolonien which turned out to be more interesting.	Scanning through the objects from lombook expedition, suddenly spotted a photo of a person with a Kris (dagger) behind. P4: "That's interesting. Yeah, you can really see the Kris here on this painting. I like that...TM-82-1... You can really see how a Kris from Lombok really looks like... I mean, it's quite useful as a way of scanning all of the different objects related to this module. (very interesting use of the filter Connected Historical Event)	
	Looking at the very first object from 1802 through visual animation and not seeing the production place, the user got curious to see what this object was and her belief was it was from US; found out it is from Singosari (Indonesia)!		Looking into the actor-actor network P3 sees "Rijksmuseum Volkenkunde" which is wereldmuseum today have only limited connection to other actors, which is not a lot! That is surprising.	Fom network visualisation, I would like to investigate the actor "Koninklijk Nederlands Aardrijkskundig Genootschap (KNAG)". From the network, saw they are connected with two institution, but now selecting just this actor can see only one institution, this was due the connection two was connected via the connection one (2 degree connection). Koninklijk Nederlands Aardrijkskundig Genootschap (KNAG) connected to Maatschappij ter Bevordering van het Natuurkundig Onderzoek der Nederlandsche Kolonien connected to G.A.J van der Sande...that rings a bell. [looking in to Van der Sande's instance page and reading Biography] A doctor....	[Looking at the actor-actor network graph] So obviously, I think what interests me is actor who are more centrally located. Obviously Colonial museum is very centrally located. The Minister of Colony is very centrally located. I'm certainly Amsterdam zoo is very centrally located. We also have again, so these are all people connected to the Colonial museum like the city, so.	
	During the demo, I was surprised to see so many objects from Morocco, I will look into objects from Morocco.			So, I have this person that I found through this network and then I go to related objects and I'll get objects that are connected to this particular person. OK.OK, cool. And this person was not directly connected to the KNAG, but to via... via.via	[Focusing on the Ministry of Colony in the actor-actor network graph] so these are all people connected to the Colonial museum ... [spotting a person visually nearby] This guy has several connections to I know the name from somewhere, Dhr. G. (Georg) Tillmann. I'm not sure. [Looking into his instance page and going into the related actor] so, he was connected to these other actors, right, and these are the objects that they have in common.... Goerg Tillman is not someone I have researched him before, but I know he is an important donor. He is a kind of person that you would like to research, so he had several links with other people, including Rautenstrauch-Joest-Museum, which is a museum in Germany I think.. A connection to a German museum is interesting because they also have a restitution debate, so it could be that we have objects coming or going to them, something like that. I am not particularly familiar with the cite... I can click on an object and see... [looking at all the different names in provenance actor] I am not entirely sure what's going on here. [clicked on to the provenance tab] So, we got it [object] 1994 from Georg Tillmann and he got it from Wolf Tillman, who got it from Rautenstrauch-Joest-Museum, who got it from Dr. Wilhelm Muller... wait we do not know that, as there is no (provenance) event date, I guess this problem comes from TMS. Still, it's interesting to me that another museum is involved here, before our museum. Now, I am interested to see who this person "Wolf Tillman" is?	

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	<p>From the actor network graph centially got interested in Actor "Natura Artis Magistra". Going back to object perspective to select the actor through "Transfer Title From" filter. Went to the Acquisition date timelines, surprised to see only two different date of acquisition.</p>	<p>one object have 9 different provenance type along its biography chain of events</p>	<p>Getting into the metadata of the actor from objects tables based on (selection, place of origin: Congo and historical event: Strafexpeditie Caica Masi.) -> P3 got to the objects connected to this actors ("related objects")</p>	<p>Looking into objects from 3 different region and transferred title from: H.C.A.E.(C.) Heimkamp now looking into the connected historical events... Yes, this person has connections with two events. Aceh and Expedtie naar Nias. That's interesting! So, there is a connection to an expedition to Nias where he likely get the object from...That's interesting. OK, then I'll zoom out again. I would, yeah. I will probably look into Heimkamp and see who this person is. But now I want to see what this Expedition to Nias...We have 23 items connected to Expedition naar Nias. Interviewer: Yeah, if you want to see all the collectors of this event, you can also go to statistics view and from the drop down here select Transferred Title From. P4: Ah, that's true. OK, two other collectors: Natura Artis Magistra and Dhr. Kapt. P.H. de vos again, we already knew these two. But yeah, this Heimkamp person is interesting.</p>	<p>Different historical events that has connections with this particular actor, like the museum. Yes. So that's interesting. How do you know this is an exhibition? I mean, is there a module for this on TMS? ... OK, so somebody filled that in. So that's interesting! (new information) Lombok Expedition->Historical event. I mean that's pretty useful, although in principle somebody had to make this (fill the information in). OK, that would be a logical way. I mean, I think a large part of the Research's job is to interpret narrow things, but it is a logical place to start with a bigger search.</p>	
	<p>Actor "Natura Artis Magistra" -> production heatmap, going back to the production place of origin, very surprised to see object from Futila. Now curious to see, what is the connected event, going back to "Connected Events" filter. Now looking into one specific objects and its provenance chain. Wanted to know more about the historical event itself going into the historical events instance page, but it doesn't gives much information from Event description. Now deselecting "Natura Artis Magistra", P1 is curious who are the actors involved with the objects related to the event "Futila (Kongo)" Going to the actor acquisition timeline trying to understand who is the actors and now search that actor and reading biography of the actor. Curious who is the related actor and found none for the selected actor. There was 4 hits with th Surname Vogelpoel, selecting all 4 of them, P1 is trying to understand if there is any connection in between them.</p>	<p>Started with Actor perspective with Actor: Gerrit Schouten -> In the remarks find out he is a oldest son of one of the Surinamies painter</p>	<p>Exploring the actor-actor network graph, found out Stichting National Museum van Wereldculturen found out 52 connection with other actor: Philip Franz Laging Tobias</p>	<p>[Again through Maatschappij linked to H.J.T. Bijlmer and mentioned in the biography -> looking in related object for H.J. T. Bijlmer] oh! That's accestral remain... A lot! Now if I want to see the acquisition date of all these objects what should I do?</p>		
		<p>Randomly going through the list of actor, clicking on Louis Christiaan Wielsink (probably curiosity) -> [getting into the actor instance page] see two different museum as related actor with lots of object -> getting into the historical event findout which historical events they have been participated in (Batak Oorlog) and commented that's very useful. Now curious to see all actor related to Batak oorlog!</p>		<p>[From H.J.T. Bijlmer got interested with one of the historical events connected to him. Going back to the first event: Central Nias-Guinea Expeditie (1920-1921)] this is the expedition I was looking for. Now I want to see the related objects to this event. [Going back to object perspective and filtered through connected historical event:Central Nias-Guinea Expeditie (1920-1921)] 345 object it says. OK, that's a lot. So ... acquisition dates...</p>	<p>[Looking at the actor-actor network graph] So obviously, I think what interests me is actor who are more centrally located. Obviously Colonial museum is very centrally located. The Minister of Colony is very centrally located. I'm certainly Amsterdam zoo is very centrally located,</p>	
					<p>From the related link of Goerg Tillmann to Wolf Tillman found out, later is the father and father's name is spelled wrong. lot's of spelling variant</p>	
					<p>In Wolf Tillman's biography, it says his connection with the current museum, but I am not sure how he is connected to the Germans. [looking into related historical event of the actor] found out connected historical event: Berliner Indonesische Expedition, which also establish connection with Wilhem Muller. That explains why German museum or person has connection with objects from Indonesia, though the Netherlands is the one who did most Colonisation there. Now, I am interested in Berliner Indonesische expedition (connected historical events)</p>	
					<p>From Berliner Indonesische expedition -> Actor-Acquisition timeline again pick interest in on the person Georg Tillman and inspecting some of the objects and their provenance events chain, P5 commented, "...[interpreting the whole story], so you can really get hang of this"</p>	

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				<p>[Going back to the first event: Central Nias-Guinea Expedition (1920-1921)] this is the expedition I was looking for. Now I want to see the related objects to this event. Interviewer: Yes. And then you go to the objects. You go to the connected historical events filter from object Perspective. You basically write down that event name here. OK. There is 19 with Nias! It's a lot of New Guinea expeditions, which I can't remember which one it was looking for. Interviewer: we can just go back... back... it is there... P4: It is 1920 - 1921. OK, we go to the objects. Oh, yeah, that's nice. And that was correct. Yeah. And then go again. Historical events, right? Can I go historical? OK. And then? OK, just write 1920. I think there that should be less. Yeah. Yeah. Ah. OK. Yes. here. This one. Ah, perfect! Go to acquisition time series. It's the easiest way. yeah. 345 object it says. OK, that's a lot. So ... acquisition dates... Nice. OK. Yeah. So it was in 1922, but then there is. So if transfer of custody... interesting, this one would be like actor acquisition time series. Then OK. Oh yeah. OK. Oh yeah, of course. Then here. Probably all three of them. Yeah, participants of the expedition or Yeah. Involve people. And then here. 2004. Try to over. I have two people here again. So these are private people or people. Yeah, that they just acquired this form. The music record from them. Yeah. In 2004 and 11. Hjt Belmar is that, then the same. That won't be. He won't be very old. It's the same person or is it like, yeah, the send them the same person? Well, we can also look into some of his objects. Sometimes there is like more than one Providence event, so you can go. This person's like this one here. Transfer title from Yeah, Transfer title from OK IT transcript person. Go to the temple. Let's investigate one of his object. Let's see. Yeah. And then go to the problems. So yeah, just don't say yes as much. So this is just the acquisition date, and this is the person appeared transit. That's that. Sometimes it's like OK person have this object but give to somebody else and we have that change as well. But in this case it's not the case. Yeah. And also doesn't. Say the 2004 one like 11-1, no, there is 686 on this one. So you need to go for all of them. Yes. It doesn't have a date for next one. Good afternoon, babe. Sure. I don't feel that I'm still looking for that 2011. OK, I have to anyways. no. But that's also something that I like would be curious and but this is something super interesting because I wouldn't have seen this in one view in a list as I saw this now in the OR was it the actor acquisition time series? Yeah, that's super interesting</p>		